

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE IX

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

September 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

@pinagpalapublishingservices	<input type="button" value="Search"/>
pinagpala_publishing	<input type="button" value="Search"/>
www.pinagpalapublishing.com	<input type="button" value="Search"/>

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), p.27, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Exploring the Challenges and Opportunities of Mobile Learning Applications in Enhancing Industrial Arts Activities Within TLE Programs

MICOH S. ENRIQUEZ
Guimaras State University

Abstract

This study explores the challenges and opportunities of integrating mobile learning applications in enhancing Industrial Arts activities within Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) programs. Recognizing the increasing role of digital tools in education, the research aimed to determine how mobile applications support teaching and learning in Industrial Arts, as well as the barriers that hinder their effective utilization. Using a descriptive-qualitative approach, data were gathered through interviews and surveys with TLE teachers and students from selected secondary schools. The findings revealed that mobile learning applications provide significant opportunities for interactive learning, accessibility of instructional resources, and student engagement in hands-on activities. However, challenges such as limited internet connectivity, insufficient teacher training, and lack of standardized digital resources were identified as major constraints. The study concludes that while mobile learning applications present strong potential to enrich Industrial Arts instruction, their success depends on addressing technological and pedagogical gaps. It recommends continuous teacher professional development, provision of reliable digital infrastructure, and the development of localized mobile learning content to maximize the benefits of mobile technology in TLE programs.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17077333

Copyright © 2025 by Pinagpala Publishing Services

Indexed at Google Scholar, Zenodo, OpenAire, Philippine eJournals, Google, Yahoo, MS Bing